

THE TYPE OF TRANSLATIONS AND APPLYING THEM ON CONSTRUCTION TERMINOLOGY.

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Annotation: this article shed lights on defining the type of translation and applying the types on translating construction terminology. It is observed that there are several types of translating method which can be used to reveal the meaning of construction terminology. However, it is obvious that if the word or word combination is a term related giving descriptive translation is prime features of construction terminology.

Key words: translation, translation methods, type of translation, construction terminology, architecture, visual aids

The introduction of new design concepts, materials, and innovative architectural solutions is leading to emerge new terms and words. New terms and words are perhaps the non-literary and the professional translator's biggest problem. New objects and processes are continually created in technology. New ideas and variations on feelings come from the media. Terms from the social sciences, slang, dialect coming into the mainstream of language, transferred words, make up the rest. A few years ago, 300 'new words were said to be counted in four successive numbers of the French weekly, L'Express. It has been stated that each language acquires 3000 new words annually. In fact, neologisms cannot be accurately quantified, since so many hover between acceptance and oblivion and many are short-lived. What is obvious is that their number is increasing steeply and as we become more language- as well as self-conscious, articles, books and specialist and general dictionaries devoted to them appear more commonly. Since they usually arise first in a response to a particular need, a majority of them have a single meaning and can therefore be translated out of context, but many of them soon acquire new (and sometimes lose the old) meanings in the target language. Newmark (1988) mentions the difference between translation methods and translation procedures. He states that translation methods relate to text as a whole, while translation procedures are used for sentences and smaller units of language. He refers to the following methods of translation:

- *Word-for-word translation:* the source language word order is preserved and the words translated singly by their most common meanings, and out of context.
- *Literal translation:* the source language grammatical constructions are converted to their nearest target language equivalents, but the lexical words are again translated singly, and out of context.
- *Faithful translation:* it attempts to produce the precise contextual meaning of the original within the constraints of the target language grammatical structures.
- *Semantic translation:* differs from faithful translation only in as far as it must take more account of the aesthetic value of the source language text.
- *Adaptation:* the freest form of translation; used mainly for plays (comedies) and poetry; the themes, characters, plots are usually preserved, the source language culture is converted to the target language culture and the text is rewritten.
- *Free translation:* it produces the target language text without the style, form, or content of the original. - *Idiomatic translation:* it reproduces the message of the original, but tends to distort nuances of meaning by preferring colloquialisms and idioms where these do not exist in the original
- *Communicative translation:* it attempts to render the exact contextual meaning of the original in a way that both content and language are readily acceptable and comprehensible to the readership.

In my opinion, and as an interpreter trainee, terms are difficult to handle as they are short and refer to a specific concept. A term is a word closely linked to a specialized conceptual content, which relates to a

specific area or field or discipline (Khan, 2016). The dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics defines a term as “a unit of expression which has universal intuitive recognition by native speakers, in both spoken and written language”. Ananiadou (1994: 1034) says that a term may be a single word or a multiword unit. There is not much literature about strategies when facing terms in the interpreting field. Khan (2016) suggests that teaching terminology during the university cursus will help translators and interpreters. According to Khan, planning terminology classes will help learners to coin new terms as they can be in critical situations where equivalents may not be found in dictionaries. There is a general consensus that terms are potentially problematic for interpreters (Amato & Mack, 2011). It is important for interpreters to have basic knowledge of the field as terms are not common in speeches. They often have no equivalent in the target listener’s cultural frame, which makes them difficult to translate into the target language. The interpreter has to choose among different interpreting strategies to deliver the message.

Additionally, The basis for the analysis is made on strategies for translating idioms, applied to terms, provided by Mona Baker (Mona Baker 2006 and Harvey 5-9). The translation/interpretation strategies used in the process of interpretation are:

- 1) Using a term/word/phrase of similar meaning and form
Using a term/word/phrase of similar meaning and form This strategy involves using a term/word/phrase in the target language which conveys roughly the same meaning as that of the source language term/word/phrase and, in addition, consists of equivalent lexical terms. This kind of match can only occasionally be achieved. (Baker, 2006)
- 2) Using a term/word/phrase of similar meaning but dissimilar form:
A term/word/phrase in target language is found, which has a similar meaning as the source term/word/phrase, but which consists of different lexical items. (Baker, 2006) This strategy was used only a few times
- 3) Translation by paraphrase
According to Baker (2006), this is the most common way of translating terms/words/phrases when a match cannot be found in the target language. This strategy is good at showing the interpreters ability to cope with an unfamiliar situation under pressure. Newmark (1988:91) states that paraphrase is ‘an amplification or explanation of the meaning’ used to clarify an ambiguous or obscure phrase.
- 4) Translation by omission
There are a number of reasons why a term/word/phrase is omitted in the target language. This may be because it has no close match in the target language, its meaning cannot be easily paraphrased, or for stylistic reasons (Baker, 2006). When it comes to simultaneous interpreting, it can be due to the time constraints, to catch up with the source language speaker. Usually, these omitted lexical items are of no great importance for the listener.
- 5) Functional equivalence
It means using a term/word/phrase in target language whose function is similar to that of the source language. Harvey (2000) writes that authors are divided over the merits of this technique; Weston describes it as the ‘ideal method of translation’ (1991:23), whereas Šarčević claims it is ‘misleading and should be avoided’ (1985:131).
- 6) Formal equivalence
Other name for this strategy is ‘linguistic equivalence’, i.e. word-for-word translation. It is mostly used when translating certain legal, political, sports or any other institutions/organization which exist or have existed in target language culture (Harvey, 2000), but also for translating other terms. Usually, the word order remains the same as in source language.
- 7) Transcription/borrowing
This strategy includes reproducing or, where necessary, phonologically adapting the original term/word/phrase. Particularly, It is used while translating architectural , most often, because it does not exist in the same form in the source language culture. Newmark (1988:82) calls it ‘transference’. Also it is often used when ‘translating’ proper names.
- 8) Conventionalization
This strategy applies to those proper names which have an established name in the target language culture. Here listed are names, brand names and names of institutions which have not been categorized in other tables.

10) Descriptive translation

A descriptive or self-explanatory translation uses generic rather than culture-bound terms to convey the meaning. It is appropriate in many contexts where formal equivalence is considered insufficiently clear (Harvey, 2000).

Translating architectural terms in simultaneous translation is a complex task that requires expertise in:

- language proficiency;
- architectural knowledge;

Architectural terms often involve specific terminology related to building materials, construction techniques, design principles, and spatial concepts. The interpreter must possess a deep understanding of these terms in both the source and target languages to accurately convey the intended meaning to the audience.

In the face of these challenges, translators of architectural terms need to strike a balance between maintaining the technical accuracy of the terminology and effectively communicating the cultural, historical, sensory and visual aspects of architecture to their target audience. Collaboration with experts in architecture and related fields can greatly aid in achieving the most accurate and nuanced translations. Translating architectural terms presents a unique set of challenges due to their technical and specialized nature. These terms often involve precise descriptions of architectural elements, materials, construction techniques, and design principles. Here are some key peculiarities to consider when translating such terms:

1. Lack of direct equivalents: many architectural terms have no direct equivalents in other languages. This is especially true for terms that refer to specific construction methods, materials, or design concepts that are unique to a particular culture or region. Translators must carefully analyze the context and meaning behind these terms to find the most appropriate translation.

2. Terminology Consistency: architecture often involves a consistent use of terminology across different documents, plans, and communication channels. Translators must maintain this consistency in the target language while adapting the terms to fit linguistic and cultural norms. This requires a deep understanding of the source and target languages as well as architectural concepts.

3. Collaboration with Expert. Updating for Contemporary trends: translators often collaborate with architects, engineers, and subject-matter experts to ensure accurate translations. This collaboration helps clarify technical details, resolve ambiguities, and provide insights into the specific terminology used in architectural documents. Architecture is a field that evolves over time with new technologies, design philosophies, and materials. Translators need to be aware of these evolving trends and update their translations accordingly to reflect modern practices and concepts.

Architectural styles, motifs, and elements are often deeply tied to the culture and history of a region. Translating these terms requires not only linguistic expertise but also a cultural understanding to capture the nuanced connotations and references. For example, the translation of terms related to traditional architecture would involve conveying aesthetic principles of harmony with nature and simplicity. It conveys cultural and historical connotations.

In tackling these challenges, translators often create glossaries or databases of architectural terms and their translations to ensure consistency across projects. Additionally, providing context, such as explanatory notes or visual aids, can enhance the understanding of the translated terms, especially for non-expert readers. The successful translation of architectural terms requires a delicate balance between technical accuracy, linguistic precision, and contextual understanding. Translating architectural terms with cultural and historical connotations is a complex task that requires a deep understanding of both the source and target cultures, as well as the historical context. Here are some of the key peculiarities associated with translating architectural terms in terms of their cultural and historical connotations:

1. Cultural Significance and historical Context: architectural styles, elements, and terminology often carry significant cultural meanings. Translators must be sensitive to the cultural implications of certain terms and ensure that these meanings are accurately conveyed in the target language. A direct translation might not

capture the same cultural nuances, so translators need to consider equivalent terms or explanations that resonate with the target culture.

Architectural terms can be tied to specific historical periods or events. When translating such terms, it is crucial to retain the historical context. For instance, terms related to ancient architectural styles or landmarks might require additional explanations to help the target audience understand their historical significance.

2. Providing Explanatory Notes: for terms with complex cultural or historical connotations, providing explanatory notes or footnotes can help the target audience better understand the significance of the term. This is particularly useful for educational or informative texts.

3. Visual Aids and Examples: including images, diagrams, or examples of the architectural elements being discussed can enhance the reader's understanding of the translated terms. Visual aids provide a visual presentation of the cultural and historical context. Taking the passage and images of bricks as a good example showcases effective illustration

4 Descriptive Detail: architectural descriptions often involve intricate details that contribute to the overall experience. Translators must determine how to balance detailed descriptions without overwhelming the reader with technical terms, ensuring that the visual and sensory essence remains intact. Architecture is a global field with diverse influences, and architectural terminology varies across languages, leading to the need for creative adaptations or explanations. In such cases, translators may opt for a descriptive approach, providing detailed explanations of the term's meaning. It refers as linguistic diversity.

Here are some suggested translations for architectural terms from English into Uzbek:

ADAPTOR -ikki xil turdagi elektr jihozini bir-biriga ulash uchun ishlatiladigan jihoz-adapter

ARABESQUE-chiziqlar bir-biri bilan yoysimon tutashuvli shakl, naqsh.

ANGLE FLOAT-ikki qirrali burchakka ega bo'lgan kurakcha, yangi quyilgan betonni tekislash uchun ishlatiladi-Andava.

AWNING- Soya qiluvchi qoplama-Naves

BASEBOARD, mopboard, scrubboard-uy devorlarining pastki qismiga biriktiriladigan uzun taxta, chaspak.

BORED LOCK-xona eshiklariga mahkamlanib o'rnatiladigan qulf.

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